

A Study to Assess the Impact of Preoperative Education on Anxiety and Postoperative Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Major Abdominal Surgery

Indrawati Rao*¹, Smital Chaudhary², Sonal Pandya³, Amar Mulla⁴

¹Principal, Government College of Nursing, Surat, Gujarat, India

²Lecturer Selection Scale Class I, Government College of Nursing, Surat, Gujarat, India

³PhD Scholar, Lecturer Class II, Government College of Nursing, Surat, Gujarat, India

⁴PhD Scholar, Lecturer Senior Scale Class I, Government College of Nursing, Surat, Gujarat, India

ABSTRACT

Background: Preoperative anxiety is a common psychological response that can adversely affect surgical outcomes. Structured preoperative education has the potential to alleviate anxiety and improve recovery. **Aim:** This study aimed to improve postoperative outcome. **Methodology:** A quasi-experimental, quantitative research design was adopted. The study was conducted at New Civil Hospital, Surat, involving 60 patients scheduled for major abdominal surgery, assigned to experimental (n = 30) and control (n = 30) groups using convenient sampling technique. Preoperative anxiety was measured using the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, and postoperative recovery was assessed using the Postoperative Quality Recovery Scale (PQRS). Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** The experimental group exhibited a significant reduction in anxiety post-intervention (mean decreased from 21.85 to 12.13, $p = 0.0048$), whereas the control group showed minimal change. **Conclusion:** Preoperative education significantly reduces anxiety and improves postoperative outcomes in patients undergoing major abdominal surgery.

Keywords: Preoperative education, anxiety, postoperative recovery, abdominal surgery, PQRS, Hamilton Anxiety Scale, quasi-experimental study

INTRODUCTION

Surgical interventions, particularly major abdominal surgeries, are associated with significant physical and psychological stress. Among these, preoperative anxiety is one of the most common psychological responses experienced by patients. This anxiety, which may arise due to fear of the unknown, anesthesia, pain, possible complications, or even death, can adversely affect perioperative outcomes. Multiple studies have established that preoperative anxiety is linked to increased postoperative pain, delayed wound healing, prolonged hospital stay, higher analgesic requirements, and reduced patient satisfaction (Guo et al., 2012). According to **Caumo et al. (2001)**, approximately **60%–80%** of patients undergoing major surgery experience moderate to severe levels of preoperative anxiety. Moreover, anxiety-related sympathetic activation can lead to hemodynamic instability during and after surgery,

compromising recovery. Preoperative education, which includes information about the surgical procedure, anesthesia, postoperative expectations, and recovery process, is considered an effective strategy to reduce preoperative anxiety. It empowers patients by enhancing their knowledge, correcting misconceptions, and fostering realistic expectations, thereby reducing fear and promoting cooperation. Evidence from various randomized controlled trials suggests that preoperative education significantly lowers anxiety levels, improves pain management, decreases postoperative complications, and shortens the length of hospital stay (Johns Hopkins Medicine, 2020; Devine, 1992). Yet, in many clinical settings, especially in resource-limited or busy hospital environments, structured preoperative education is often overlooked or inadequately provided.

Need of the study:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Given the high prevalence of preoperative anxiety and its negative impact on surgical outcomes, there is a crucial need to explore and implement non-pharmacological interventions that can improve patient care and safety. Major abdominal surgeries often require extensive recovery time, and anxiety can further complicate this process, leading to poor surgical outcomes and increased healthcare costs. In India, where the healthcare system is burdened with a high volume of surgical cases and often limited time for individualized patient education, standardized preoperative counseling is rarely practiced.

Maheshwari et al. (2016) studied preoperative anxiety in Indian surgical patients and found that **70%** experienced moderate to severe anxiety prior to surgery. The anxiety was significantly associated with postoperative pain and delayed mobilization. The authors emphasized the importance of addressing psychological preparedness to improve surgical outcomes.

Johns Hopkins Medicine (2020) emphasized the use of multidisciplinary preoperative education clinics. Their internal data showed a 30% reduction in anxiety levels, 25% decrease in pain scores, and improved discharge outcomes.

Verma et al. (2017) conducted a cross-sectional study in a government hospital in India and found that only 20% of surgical patients received any form of structured preoperative education. Majority relied on verbal assurances, leading to inadequate preparation and increased anxiety. The authors recommended that structured protocols be integrated into nursing practice.

Chinnasamy et al. (2018) implemented a structured preoperative education module in a tertiary hospital in South India. Their findings showed significant improvements in patients' knowledge, reduced anxiety levels, and early mobilization postoperatively.

Furthermore, the **World Health Organization (WHO)** and the **American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA)** emphasize the importance of addressing patients' psychological needs as part of holistic perioperative care. A structured preoperative educational program not only benefits the patients psychologically but also enhances clinical efficiency,

reduces medication dependency, and supports early mobilization post-surgery. Despite the high prevalence of preoperative anxiety among patients undergoing major abdominal surgery and its known negative impact on postoperative outcomes, structured preoperative education is not routinely provided in many clinical settings. There is a lack of consistent implementation of evidence-based, non-pharmacological interventions to reduce anxiety and improve surgical recovery. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the impact of structured preoperative education on preoperative anxiety and postoperative outcomes in patients undergoing major abdominal surgery.

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the study were to;

1. assess the preoperative anxiety levels among patients undergoing major abdominal surgery.
2. evaluate the effectiveness of structured preoperative education in reducing postoperative anxiety among patients undergoing major abdominal surgery.
3. assess the impact of structured preoperative education on postoperative outcomes such as pain level, mobilization, complications, and length of hospital stay between patients who received preoperative education and those who did not.
4. determine the association between preoperative anxiety levels and selected demographic variables among patients undergoing major abdominal surgery.

METHODOLOGY:

Research Approach: Quantitative, Evaluative approach

Research Design: Time series quasi experimental study design

Setting of the study: New Civil Hospital, Surat with a surgical unit performing major abdominal surgeries

Population: All adult patients (aged 18–65 years) scheduled for elective major abdominal surgery.

Sample Size: Based on a power analysis, approximately 60 patients (30 in each group) to detect

a moderate effect size with 80% power and 5% level of significance.

Sampling Technique: Convenient Sampling Technique

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients scheduled for elective major abdominal surgery.
- Patients aged 18 to 65 years.
- Patients who can understand the language of instruction.
- Patients who provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Emergency surgical cases.
- Patients with diagnosed psychiatric illnesses.
- Patients with hearing, visual, or cognitive impairments affecting communication.

- Patients undergoing minor or laparoscopic surgeries.

Data Collection tools:

Tool 1: Demographic profile and clinical data sheet

Tool 2: Postoperative Quality of Recovery Scale (PQRS)

Tool 3: Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale

Ethical Considerations:

- Approval from Institutional Ethical Committee.
- Informed written consent from all participants.
- Confidentiality and anonymity ensured.
- Participant free to withdraw at any stage

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

TABLE 4.1: Frequency and Percentage wise distribution of Samples based on Demographic Data.

Variables	Experimental group (n=30)		Control group (n=30)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Age in years				
18 or near 18	0	0	0	0
between 19-50	28	93.33%	25	83.33%
50 or more than 50	2	6.66%	5	16.66%
Sex				
Male	18	60%	18	60%
Female	12	40%	12	40%
Transgender	0	0	0	0
Religion				
Hindu	25	83.33%	26	86.66%
Muslim	5	16.66%	4	13.33%
Christian	0	0	0	0
Sikh	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0
Marital status				
Married	29	96.66%	28	93.33%
Unmarried	1	3.33%	2	6.66%
Divorced	0	0	0	0
Widowed	0	0	0	0
Types of family				
Joint	15	50%	18	60%
Nuclear	15	50%	11	36.66%
Extended	0	0	1	3.33%
Residential area				
Urban	14	46.66%	13	43.39%
Rural	13	43.33%	10	16.66%
Town	3	10%	7	11.66%
Highest level of Education				
Primary	20	66.66%	23	76.67%

Secondary	8	26.66%	7	23.30%
Higher secondary	0	0	0	0
Greduate and above	2	6.66%	0	0
Family's Monthly income				
<10000	10	33.33%	10	33.33%
10001-20000	18	60%	17	56.66%
21001-30000	1	3.33%	3	10%
>30000	1	3.33%	0	0
Major abdominal surgery				
Appendectomy	14	47%	14	47%
Cholecystectomy	11	36.66%	11	36.66%
Hernia repair	4	13%	4	13%
Other	1	3.33%	1	3.33%
Previous surgery				
Minor	0	0	0	0
Major	4	13.33%	0	0
No	26	86.66%	30	100%
Comorbidities				
None	29	96.66%	26	86.66%
Diabetes mellitus	0	0	1	3.33%
Hyper tension	1	3.33%	3	10%
Respiratory illness	0	0	0	0
Cancer	0	0	0	0
Renal failure	0	0	0	0

Table 4.5: Comparison of the Level of Anxiety in Experimental and control Group Before surgery and After Surgery.

Level of Anxiety	Experimental Group				Control Group			
	Pre test		Post test		Pretest		Posttest	
	F	%	f	%	F	%	f	%
Mild (0-17)	7	23.33%	16	53.33%	13	43.33%	10	33.33%
Moderate (18-24)	13	43.33%	11	36.66%	9	30.00%	10	33.33%
Severe (25-30)	7	23.33%	3	10%	6	20.00%	6	20%
Extreme (31-56)	3	10%	0	0.00%	2	7%	4	13.33%

Table 4.9: Distribution of Subjects According to Level of Pain on 1st and 3rd Post-Op Day

Level of Pain	Range	Post-op Day 1				Post-op Day 3			
		Experimental (n=30)		Control (n=30)		Experimental		Control (n=30)	
		F	%	f	%	F	%	F	%
No Pain	0	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Mild Pain	1 to 3	10	33.33%	4	13.33%	14	46.66%	5	16.67%
Moderate Pain	4 to 6	16	53.33%	18	60%	15	50%	21	70%
Severe Pain	7 to 9	4	13.33%	8	26.67%	1	3.33%	4	13.33%
Extreme Pain	10	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%

Comparison of Mean, Standard deviation T value parameters according to Experimental Group and And P value with their percentage of Physiological Control group post test Day 1 and Day 3

Parameters	Post Day 1				T test	P Value
	Experimental group		Control group			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
SBP	122.15	4.91	124.52	3.72	-2.1	0.0398

DBP	77.81	2.73	79.64	2.79	-2.56	0.0132
Pulse	83.65	1.6	82.82	1.14	2.15	0.0358
Respiration	20.82	0.5	21.14	0.47	-2.54	0.0138
SPO2	96.02	0.36	95.74	0.47	2.64	0.0107
Post Day 3						
Parameters	Experimental group		Control group		t value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
SBP	121.01	3.93	123.52	3.72	-2.54	0.0139
DBP	76.73	2.95	78.64	2.79	-2.57	0.0127
Pulse	82.45	1.96	83.76	1.86	-2.64	0.0106
Respiration	20.62	0.61	20.94	0.47	-2.26	0.0278
SPO2	96.17	0.36	95.96	0.28	2.53	0.014

- **Memory testing:** Statistically, on Post Day 1, the control group demonstrated a marginally higher mean score ($M = 1.33$, $SD \approx \text{constant}$) compared to the experimental group ($M = 1.07$, $SD \approx \text{constant}$). By Post Day 3, both groups exhibited a reduction in mean scores; however, the experimental group reported a lower mean ($M = 0.87$) than the control group ($M = 1.03$), indicating a greater improvement in memory performance. The standard deviations remained relatively stable across groups and time points, suggesting homogeneity of variance. These results suggest a statistically observable trend toward enhanced memory outcomes in the experimental group by Day 3, supporting the potential efficacy of the intervention.
- **Level of Attention testing:** Statistically, the experimental group exhibited a greater reduction in mean scores from Post Day 1 ($M = 1.07$) to Post Day 3 ($M = 0.87$), suggesting a notable improvement in attention assuming lower scores reflect better outcomes. In contrast, the control group showed a smaller decrease in mean scores from Day 1 ($M = 1.33$) to Day 3 ($M = 1.03$). This greater change in the experimental group indicates a potentially more effective intervention, with the consistent standard deviations across groups supporting the reliability of this observed difference.

On both Postoperative Day 1 and Day 3, the experimental group exhibited lower mean ADL scores compared to the control group, suggesting improved recovery in functional status (assuming lower scores indicate better performance). The control group maintained a consistent mean ADL score of 7.5

across both time points, whereas the experimental group demonstrated a slight decrease in mean ADL score from Day 1 to Day 3, indicating progressive improvement. Additionally, the standard deviation was higher in the control group, reflecting greater variability in ADL performance among participants, while the experimental group showed more consistent outcomes.

P-Value Analysis:

- **Postoperative Day 1:** $p = 6.49 \times 10^{-16}$
- **Postoperative Day 3:** $p = 1.21 \times 10^{-9}$

Both p-values are well below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, indicating statistically significant differences in ADL scores between the control and experimental groups at both time points.

Conclusion:

These findings provide strong statistical evidence that the preoperative education intervention had a significant positive impact on postoperative recovery in terms of Activity of Daily Living (ADL) performance among patients undergoing major abdominal surgery. The experimental group exhibited a meaningful reduction in anxiety levels from Postoperative Day 1 ($M = 14.77$) to Day 3 ($M = 12.13$), indicating a positive trend toward reduced psychological distress. In contrast, the control group showed minimal improvement, with anxiety scores decreasing slightly from 21.13 to 20.3, reflecting persistently elevated anxiety levels.

T-Value and P-Value Interpretation:

The greater *t*-value and significantly lower *p*-value observed on Postoperative Day 3 further support the conclusion that the reduction in anxiety within the experimental group was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), and unlikely to be due to random variation. This suggests that the impact of the intervention became more pronounced over time.

Conclusion:

These findings indicate that the intervention had a statistically significant effect in reducing anxiety levels among patients in the experimental group, particularly by Day 3, highlighting its potential efficacy in improving psychological recovery following surgery.

Comparison of the Total Recovery Score in Control Group and Experimental

Group in Post Day 1 and Post Day 3

		Total Recovery Score							
		Experimental group				Control Group			
	Score	post day 1		post day3		post day 1		post day 3	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	F	%
Fully Recovered	0-28	18	60.00%	24	80%	10	33.33%	13	43.33%
Partially recovered	28-52	12	40.00%	6	20%	20	66.66%	17	56.66%
Not recovered	52-93	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%

The experimental group demonstrated a notable reduction in total recovery scores from Day 1 (M = 24.4) to Day 3 (M = 19.2), indicating a marked improvement in recovery status over time. While the control group also exhibited a decline in recovery scores over the same period, their mean scores remained consistently higher than those of the experimental group, suggesting comparatively poorer recovery.

P-Value Interpretation:

On Postoperative Day 3, the *p*-value was **0.002**, which is well below the standard threshold of $p < 0.05$. This indicates a statistically significant difference in recovery outcomes between the two groups and suggests that the observed improvements in the experimental group are unlikely to have occurred by chance.

CONCLUSION:

The statistically significant reduction in recovery scores in the experimental group, compared to the control group, supports the effectiveness of the intervention. These results provide strong evidence that the intervention contributed to enhanced postoperative recovery.

Association Between Demographic Variables and Pre-Test Anxiety Levels:

Among the demographic variables analyzed, only **residential area** demonstrated a statistically significant association with pre-test anxiety levels ($p = 0.04$), indicating that the place of residence may influence preoperative anxiety. In contrast, all other variables—including age, sex, religion, marital status, family type, educational status, monthly income, type of surgery, history of previous surgery, and presence of comorbidities—had *p*-values greater than 0.05, signifying no statistically significant associations.

Recommendations for Future Research:

Future studies can explore preoperative anxiety levels among patients undergoing a wider range of surgical procedures beyond abdominal surgery. Comparative research could be designed to assess anxiety levels in patients scheduled for elective versus emergency abdominal surgeries, offering insights into how urgency influences psychological readiness. Further investigation is warranted into the effectiveness of various anxiety-reducing interventions, such as preoperative counseling, relaxation techniques, guided imagery, and pharmacological approaches, in improving patient outcomes immediately before surgery. A comparative study could also be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of individualized versus group-based preoperative education, in terms of their impact on postoperative recovery and patient satisfaction. Additionally, research should examine

the role of family involvement in preoperative education and its influence on patient recovery outcomes, recognizing the potential benefits of social support in surgical preparedness and recovery.

REFERENCE

1. Caumo, W., Schmidt, A. P., Schneider, C. N., Bergmann, J., Iwamoto, C. W., Adamatti, L. C., ... & Ferreira, M. B. C. (2001). Risk factors for preoperative anxiety in adults. *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica*, 45(3), 298–307.
2. Maheshwari, D., Ismail, S., & Prasad, T. (2016). Assessment of preoperative anxiety and its association with postoperative pain in patients undergoing abdominal surgery. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 6(9), 120–126.
3. Devine, E. C. (1992). Effects of psychoeducational care for adult surgical patients: a meta-analysis of 191 studies. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 19(2), 129–142.
4. Guo, P., East, L., & Arthur, A. (2012). A preoperative education intervention to reduce anxiety and improve recovery among Chinese cardiac patients: a randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 49(2), 129–137.
5. Kehlet, H., & Wilmore, D. W. (2002). Multimodal strategies to improve surgical outcome. *The American Journal of Surgery*, 183(6), 630–641.
6. Giraudet-Le Quintrec, J. S., Coste, J., Vastel, L., et al. (2003). Positive effect of patient education for hip surgery: a randomized trial. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, 414, 112–120.
7. Johns Hopkins Medicine. (2020). Preparing for Surgery: Reducing Anxiety Through Education. Retrieved from: <https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/>.

HOW TO CITE: Indrawati Rao*, Smital Chaudhary, Sonal Pandya, Amar Mulla, A Study to Assess the Impact of Preoperative Education on Anxiety and Postoperative Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Major Abdominal Surgery, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (2), 53-59. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18519185>